

The Factors that Affect Foodways in Nigerian Food Marketing

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Citations - APA

Ogbuke, J. C., Ejionueme, N. & Ikenna, C. (2024). The Factors that Affect Foodways in Nigerian Food Marketing. *Global Journal of Finance and Business Review*, 7(2), 63-79. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10973020>

The study was on the factors that affect foodways in Nigerian food marketing. Its specific objectives are to: examine the nutritional concerns of a household as a factor that affects foodways in Nigerian food marketing; assess multicultural society as a factor that affects foodways in Nigerian food marketing and evaluate the household disposable income as a factor that affects foodways in Nigerian food marketing. The data used in the study were taken from the survey of households from selected areas in Enugu metropolis. A questionnaire was employed to collect quantitative data. Enugu metropolis is known for its area divisions made up of New Haven, Camp, Independence Layout, Trans Ekulu, Abakpa, G.R.A., Garki etc. The study population was drawn from three areas: Abakpa, New, and Trans Ekulu. In all 98 households were involved in the study. All households were categorized based on a number of years of marriage ranging from a minimum of five years to a maximum of twenty-five years. Three hypotheses were tested using regression analysis, F-statistics (ANOVA), with aid of Special Package for Statistical Software (SPSS). The findings in the study included; that Nutritional concerns of a household have significant effect on foodways in Nigerian food marketing $F(95,n=98)= 12421.457, p<0.05$; Multicultural society has significant effect on foodways in Nigerian food marketing, hence $F(95,n=98)= 9125.514, p<0.05$; Household disposable income has significant effect on foodways in Nigerian food marketing, hence $F(95,n=275)= 7975.741, p<0.05$; The study concluded that the study concluded that the nutritional concerns, multicultural society and the household disposable income are factors that affect food ways in Nigerian food marketing. The study recommended that the nutritional concerns should be a target of any household because it is important to have a balanced diet and equally expand your diet; Multicultural society should be encouraged because many advantages lie in diversity as many individuals from a different angle of the country possess different skills which can be maximized by these institutions and government should create room for self-reliance by increasing vocational skills training to enhance household income levels to meet up with their needs.

←
ABSTRACT

Keywords: Nigerian Food Marketing; Foodways; Nutritional Concerns; Enugu Metropolis

Background

To survive we need to eat. Yet, food is more than a source of energy and nutrients essential for human health and well being. What we eat, how we eat, and when we eat reflect the complexity of wide cultural arrangements around food and foodways, the unique organization of food systems, and existing social policies (Koc, 2014). Food plays a key role in human socialization, in developing an awareness of body and self, language acquisition, and personality development. As Barthes (1975) argues substances, techniques of preparation, habits, all become part of a system of differences in signification and we communicate by way of food. As we learn what to eat, how to eat when to eat, we learn "our" culture, "our" norms and "our" values and through this process, we learn who "we" are.

Food availability for households in urban and rural areas means assurance that they can access sufficient food through their own production or through purchase from markets, given sufficient purchasing power. Food access is ensured when households, and all individuals within them, have adequate resources to obtain appropriate foods for a nutritious diet (Agada and Igbokwe, 2016). Availability of food and access to food can be influenced largely by marketing engaged in by those in the agricultural sector. Agricultural marketing is a form of marketing that encompasses all goods and services related to the field of agriculture (Ikporah, 2012). All these products directly or indirectly support the effort to produce and deliver agricultural products from the farm to the consumer. The range of this type of marketing includes such varied products as real estate support, equipment used in cultivation and harvesting, storage facilities for harvested crops, and delivery services that transport the harvest to consumers (Ikporah, 2012). In addition, financial services that make it possible to secure products necessary for agriculture to function are also normally included as part of agricultural marketing.

In the last 5 years, Nigeria's share of global food consumption has averaged 3.4%, the highest amongst all African countries (PWC, 2017). However, its food supply, consumption, and marketing suffer from various setbacks ranging from shortage of supply, price fluctuations, poor distribution and length of chain, spoilage in transit, inflation, variety choice and nutritional concerns of households of households, etc. (Tomek and Robinson, 1981). This possibility of factors to affect food ways is the interest of this study.

Statement of the Problem

Without access to healthy foods, a nutritious diet and good health are out of reach. And without central markets, grocery stores and other fresh food retailers, communities are missing the commercial hubs that make neighborhoods livable and help local economies thrive. Marketing serves as the platform that links customers to these stores and markets. The food and marketing link literature is dominated by studies seeking to link demographic, economic, and spatial data with health outcomes, with little attention to what matters to people, or what they actually do to acquire food. This raises the need to understand factors that affect foodways in Nigerian food marketing.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is factors that affect foodways in Nigerian food marketing. Its specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the nutritional concerns of a household as a factor that affects foodways in Nigerian food marketing.
2. Assess multicultural society as a factor that affects foodways in Nigerian food marketing.
3. Evaluate the household disposable income as a factor that affects foodways in Nigerian food marketing.

Research Questions

1. What is the effect of nutritional concerns of a household as a factor that affects foodways in Nigerian food marketing?
2. What is the effect of multicultural society as a factor that affects foodways in Nigerian food marketing?
3. What is the effect of the household disposable income as a factor that affects foodways in Nigerian food marketing?

Statement of the Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study

1. Nutritional concerns of a household have no significant effect on foodways in Nigerian food marketing
2. Multicultural society has no significant effect on foodways in Nigerian food marketing
3. Household disposable income has no significant effect on foodways in Nigerian food marketing

Review of Literature

Conceptional Framework

Food Ways

Food is a basic necessity of life. Food is more than a basic source of nutrients; it is also a key component of our culture, central to our sense of identity. Foodways is the study of what we eat, as well as how and why and under what circumstances we eat it. It encompasses the whole interrelated system of food conceptualization and evaluation, procurement, preservation, preparation, consumption, and nutrition shared by all the members of a particular society. This broad definition embraces both historical and regional differences while simultaneously pointing to the importance of food events, food processes and even the aesthetic realms that touch upon the world of food.

Food Marketing

Food marketing is defined as the activities that take place within the food system between the farm gate and the consumer. This includes processing, wholesaling, retailing, food service, and transportation functions and excludes all functions performed by producers on the farm. The marketing system performs the services necessary to move food from the producer to the consumer. Most products are processed, packaged, stored, and transported as they move through the marketing channels. The extent and type of these operations depend on the nature of the product and its location relative to the consumer. In addition to farm production, energy, labor, and other inputs are utilized by firms to perform marketing functions. Finally, there must be a flow of information to facilitate the orderly exchange of goods and services among firms in the marketing system.

The Nutritional Concern

Nutritional concern is a process of having a sufficient protein in your body. But if you eat beans, whole grains, nuts and seeds, you should be okay. Non-vegan vegetarians may eat eggs and dairy products, too, which contain a lot of protein. Most people focus on the total calories, but one amount of protein and calories from fat is important too. Although cellulose has no nutritional value, it does have a lot of fiber. Fiber is particularly helpful for digestive purposes (Plawecki, 2011). For the same reason that gas or diesel is necessary for a car. Fuel is needed to supply energy to the engine. Food is the fuel for our bodies. When we live we burn calories and they must be replaced. No fuel, no run. No food, no life. it is important to have a balanced diet because if you get overweight you could get obese. Restricted diets can cause allergies...when improving your diet, instead of thinking of "restricting" your diet, "expand" your diet. For example, instead of just abstaining from meat, increase the variety of your fruit and vegetable intake. Eat different types of beans and protein foods. Try grain alternatives instead of eating say, wheat all the time. A variety of foods will help ensure you get all the nutrients you need and help you avoid autoimmune illnesses. It is good to eat a bit of all the food groups each day, and make sure to have plenty of calcium and other nutrients (Weaver, 2012).

Multicultural Society

A multicultural society is a system, a set of interrelated parts, in this case, beliefs and behaviours which make up the whole of how humans experience today's world. It includes what people believe about others, their basic paradigms, and how these impact, and are impacted by, behaviour. The outcome of this framework of beliefs/behaviours are seven important actions. The first is recognition of the rich diversity in a given society or organization. For the longest time racial/ethnic minorities, the physically disabled, and women have not been given the same recognition as

others. The one-sided approach to history and education has been a testimony to that fact. With recognition should also come respect. Respect and recognition are not the same, since recognizing the existence of a group does not necessarily elicit respect for the group. In a slave economy, for example, the presence of slaves was recognized but their humanity was not respected. The presence of American Indians in the Western expansion of the continent was constantly recognized by whites, but their environmentally conscious cultures were never respected. Caleb (2018). The contribution of women has usually been relegated to a footnote status. Our nation has a long history of not respecting the rights of the powerless. Multicultural society also entails acknowledging the validity of the cultural expressions and contributions of the various groups. This is not to imply that all cultural contributions are of equal value and social worth, or that all should be tolerated. Some cultural practices are better than others for the overall betterment of society. These cultural expressions and contributions that differ from those of the dominant group in society are usually only acknowledged when there is an economic market for them, such as music for African American, native Indian dances for tourism or Mexican cuisine. When the business sector wants our money, the advertising industry pictures people of color in a positive light. But in most other cases the entertainment media simply caricatures minority stereotypes, such as women usually in supportive roles. Multiculturalism thus means *valuing* what people have to offer, and not rejecting or belittling it simply because it differs from what the majority, or those in power, regard as important and of value (Caleb, 2018).

Household Disposable Income

Household disposable income is defined as the sum of household final consumption expenditure and savings, minus the change in net equity of households in pension funds. This indicator also corresponds to the sum of wages and salaries, mixed income, net property income, net current transfers and social benefits other than social transfers in kind, less taxes on income and wealth and social security contributions paid by employees, the self-employed and the unemployed. Household gross adjusted disposable income additionally reallocates "income" from government and non-profit institutions serving households (NPISHs) to households to reflect social transfers in kind. These transfers reflect expenditures made by government or NPISHs on individual goods and services, such as health and education, on behalf of an individual household. The indicator includes the disposable income of non-profit institutions serving households. Disposable income, as a concept, is closer to the idea of income as generally understood in economics, than is either national income or gross domestic product (GDP). This indicator is measured in terms of net in annual growth rates and in terms of gross adjusted in USD per capita at current prices and PPPs. OECD (2016). In economics, disposable income refers to household income after deducting mandatory taxes, such as state and federal income tax, Social Security and Medicare. Another term that you might often see is "discretionary income," which refers to household income after paying for necessities, such as food, housing costs, insurance and utilities. It's important to note that the boundary between mandatory and voluntary deductions is quite strict: Even though you may consider deductions made for health insurance and your 401k to be essential, they are still considered as optional expenses because you choose to have insurance coverage and a retirement plan. Lainie, (2018).

The Concept of Stable Value

The stable value is the Changes in the purchasing power of money, i.e., in the exchange ratio between money and vendible goods and commodities, which can originate either from the side of money or from the side of the vendible goods and commodities. The change in the data which provokes them can occur either in the demand for and supply of money or in the demand for and supply of the other goods and services. The stable monetary unit concept assumes that the value of the dollar is stable over time. This concept essentially allows accountants to disregard the effect of inflation -- a decrease, in terms of real goods, of what a dollar can purchase. Because of this assumption, past financial statements are usually not updated even if the value of money substantially changes. The concept is generally a practical necessity, even though the assumption can present some serious challenges if the currency is either deflating or inflating quickly (Matt, 2017). Though the stable monetary unit assumption makes the process of accounting more manageable, it can sometimes present problems. If the value of money rapidly changes due to market conditions or the effects of policy, a business's financial statements may be less useful for comparison with prior records. If the values of accounts or past statements are not subsequently adjusted to address the inflation or

deflation, the accounting record may not accurately represent a business's financial performance. This issue presents a link between day-to-day accounting practice and broader market trends or government policy (Forbes, 2012).

Theoretical Framework

George Akerlof's (1973) Asymmetric information theory guided the study.

The theoretical basis for the study is the Asymmetric information theory. Asymmetric information, as the adjective indicates, refers to situations, in which some agent in a trade possesses information while other agents involved in the same trade do not. When information is asymmetric, prices are distorted and do not achieve optimality in the allocation of resources. The term originates with George Akerlof's study of the market for cars. Akerlof's mathematical model (1973, 489-92) contrasts a state in which a seller knows the quality of the car he has to sell, while the buyer does not, with an earlier state in which seller and buyer have the same information. Akerlof identifies the gain in utility arising from the symmetrical state of information, as compared with the asymmetric state. The term 'asymmetric information' has, however, come to be used more loosely for circumstances in which one agent is better informed than another, without contrasting that position with a position of asymmetric information. In Stiglitz's account (2002, 469) it refers specifically to the 'fact that different people know different things'. The contrast is more with the state of perfect information assumed in the neoclassical model than with a position of asymmetric information, in the sense of equal information. The term 'asymmetric information' is then not entirely apt. People having the same information is not the same as perfect information, even if perfect information implies that everyone has the same perfect information. An assumption that people have the same information would be almost as absurd in the real world as the assumption of perfect information. It would hardly be appropriate in a thesis like that of Stiglitz, which tries to take neoclassical theory closer to reality. There seem to be no theories, other than that of Akerlof (1970), that specifically identify or conceive symmetric information as a 'base case', least of all common understanding. The focus on 'asymmetric information' rather than simply imperfect information means that the information issues even within the neoclassical model are not, as Stiglitz (2002, p. 473) recognizes, fully covered by analysis of asymmetric information. But more importantly, the discussion of 'asymmetric information', conducted within the confines of neoclassical theory, fails to deal with the information issues of the real world.

Empirical Review

Agada and Igbokwe (2016) assessed the influence of food culture and practices on household food security among Tiv, Igala, and Eggon ethnic groups in North Central Nigeria in 2011. A sample of 120 Tiv, 108 Igala, and 112 Eggon households was interviewed using a structured questionnaire and focus group discussion. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and a logistic regression procedure. Findings revealed that all households consumed carbohydrate-based foods, men (93%) dominated agricultural decision making and undertake land preparation and ridging while women carried out weeding and food processing. All households practiced subsistence farming, 94.7% practiced mixed cropping, 93% acquired farmland through inheritance and 67% sourced farm labor from the family. Males controlled household income (95%) and had a preference in household food sharing (78%). Food culture and practices that significantly influenced household food security were control over household income (-1.056; $p \leq 0.05$) and preference over household food sharing (0.834; $p \leq 0.05$). The study concluded that culture was a dominant factor in a number of meals consumed per day, household food choices, agricultural decision making, cropping system, a division of labor, land acquisition, control over household income, preference in household food sharing and hence food security. It is recommended that both male and female farmers should be encouraged to diversify their income sources and make more money accessible for food purchases. Also, both genders should be provided access to productive resources for increased agricultural production and productivity for food security. Furthermore, farmers should be encouraged to produce and consume food of increased quality and diversity for improved nutrition and food security and household food should be fairly distributed in order to take care of the nutritional needs of all family members.

Abu and Soom (2016) examined factors affecting household food security status among rural and urban farming households of Benue State, Nigeria. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were employed to obtain a sample of 180 respondents, 90 households head each from rural and urban areas. Data were collected through structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics, Food Security Index, Surplus/Food Insecurity Gap, Factor analysis, and Probit model. Using calorie intake method, the result revealed that 53.3% and 62.2% of rural

and urban households respectively were food secured. The rural and urban food secure households exceeded the recommended calorie intake by 39% and 42% respectively, while the rural and urban food insecure households fell short of recommended calorie by 24% and 26% respectively. It was also found that income of households head ($p < 0.10$), rural households size ($p < 0.01$), and farm size ($p < 0.10$) had a positive impact on household food security. On the other hand, the age of the household head ($p < 0.05$) and urban household size ($p < 0.10$) had a negative relationship with household food security. Constraints such as lack of access to credits, inadequate land availability, and poverty, infertility of the soil, lack of non-farm income generating activities, storage and processing problems were identified as some of the factors militating against the achievement of food security in the study area. It was recommended that credit be provided to farming households by government to reduce the constraint of not being able to access credit facilities, the agricultural policies which aimed at promoting farmers access to land and improving farm household productivity be encouraged and that farmers be provided with informal education through extension services on nutritional awareness and non-farm income-generating activities.

Agbogo, Udouso, and Tiku (2013) evaluated the factors affecting rice consumption in the Cross River State of Nigeria. Two hundred and forty (240) rice consumers were randomly selected from twelve (12) purposively selected Local Government Areas in Cross River State. Data were collected using a questionnaire. It was discovered that the socio-economic variables that affect rice consumers in the study area were age, marital status, household size, religion and educational level. It was also found that the average monthly income of a respondent, the average amount spent on rice per day by one household and the average quantity of rice consumed per meal per household were N32,154.00, N1,378.00 and 2kg respectively. The results showed that the coefficients of the four explanatory variables selected for the study met the a priori theoretical expectations. The variables included rice consumers disposable income (X1t), occupational status of the consumers (D1t), the joint effect of income and occupational status (D1tX1t), a brand of rice (D2t), the price of rice (X2t) and the joint effect of rice brand and own price (D2tX2t). The results showed that disposable income variable had a magnitude of 0.352 and was positive, brand had a magnitude of 0.378 and was equally positive, price had a negative magnitude of -0.121, occupational status variable had a positive magnitude of 0.372, while the joint effects of income and occupational status and rice brand and own price were 0.243 and 0.131 respectively. The implication of the results is that anyone unit change in income, occupational status of the rice consumers, brand and price in the study area will result in an increase of 0.352, 0.372, 0.134 and -0.121 units respectively. The negative sign of the coefficient of the price of rice is in consonance with the theoretical expectation. In order words, price naturally has an inverse relationship with consumption expenditure, where an increase in income results in less of the commodity consumed. It is therefore recommended that Governments should provide employment opportunities for the people in order to enhance their income levels, as well as make policies that would encourage local rice production, in order to meet the demand and make rice available to consumers at an affordable price in the study area. Also, farmers should be encouraged to produce more of the brand of rice available in the area.

Egbetokun and Omonona (2012) accessed the determinants of farmers' participation in a food market in Odeda L.G.A. of Ogun state. Simple random sampling technique was used in the selection of the respondents and a well-structured question was used to gather information on the determinants of farmers' participation in a food market. A total of 100 questionnaires were administered but only 70 could be retrieved and subjected to analysis. The analytical technique includes descriptive statistics and Probit regression analysis. The result shows that the average age was 45yrs. Probit analysis shows that the major determining factors influencing farmers participation in the market were age, marital status, the source of labor, farming experience, farm size, and which were significant at $p \leq 0.05$ and $p \leq 0.01$ respectively. It is therefore recommended that government should intensify efforts through the extension agents in organizing programs which will enhance farmers' participation in the market through training, disseminating market information and better utilization of farmland.

Babatunde and Oyatoye (2005) examined problems of food marketing and security in Nigeria, using maize marketing in Kwara State as a case study. This is against the background of persistent food crisis being experienced for sometimes now in the country. Primary data were collected during the 1997/98 farming season from two hundred food marketers consisting of eighty wholesalers and one hundred and twenty retailers spread across six local government areas of the state. Secondary data were collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and annual reports. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Market margin, distribution of total market margin and marketing efficiency were estimated. The results indicate that the average

farm-gate price of maize was N755 per 50kg bag of maize. The average marketing cost was N105.3/bag and the average net marketing margin was N158.2/bag. The average marketing efficiency was 143.5% in the study area. The distribution of total marketing margin shows that the wholesalers' share was 68.1% and the retailers' share was 31.9% on the average. When compared with the farmer's return, the middlemen's share of total marketing margin was higher. This is perceived as market exploitation because not much value is added to the food by the middlemen to justify the very high margin collected. This "exploitation" directly or indirectly leads to loss of interest in farming and subsequently food insecurity in the country. Responses of the selected respondents show that the major problems of food marketing are; transportation problem, inadequate market infrastructure, inadequate funding, shortage of processing facilities and seasonality and perishability of food produce. To improve food marketing and food security situation in Nigeria, it is recommended that adequate transportation facilities, in terms of good roads and functional vehicles should be provided by the government, private individuals and cooperative groups. Also, research into post-harvest storage and processing techniques should be intensified and finally, the fund should be made available, through both formal and informal sources, to food marketers so that they can take advantage of bulk purchasing, market expansion, and postharvest processing.

Methodology

The data used in the study were taken from the survey of households from selected areas in Enugu metropolis. A questionnaire was employed to collect quantitative data. Enugu metropolis is known for its area divisions made up of New Haven, Camp, Independence Layout, Trans Ekulu, Abakpa, G.R.A., Garki etc. The study population was drawn from three areas: Abakpa, New, and Trans Ekulu. In all 98 households were involved in the study. All households were categorized based on a number of years of marriage ranging from a minimum of five years to a maximum of twenty-five years.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Response on the nutritional concerns of a household as a factor that affects Foodways in Nigerian food marketing.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	34	34.7	34.7	34.7
	Agree	28	28.6	28.6	63.3
	Neutral	14	14.3	14.3	77.6
	Disagree	10	10.2	10.2	87.8
	strongly disagree	12	12.2	12.2	100.0
	Total	98	100.0	100.0	

From Table 1 indicated that 34 respondents out of 98 representing 34.7 percent strongly agree, 28 respondents representing 28.6 percent agree that the nutritional concerns of a household as a factor that affects foodways in Nigerian food marketing. 14 respondents representing 14.3 percent were neutral, 10 respondents representing 10.2 percent disagreed and 12 respondents representing 12.2 percent strongly disagree.

Table 2 Response on multicultural society as a factor that affects foodways in Nigerian food marketing.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	35	35.7	35.7	35.7
	Agree	32	32.7	32.7	68.4
	Neutral	8	8.2	8.2	76.5
	Disagree	6	6.1	6.1	82.7
	strongly disagree	17	17.3	17.3	100.0
	Total	98	100.0	100.0	

From Table 2 indicates that 35 respondents out of 98 representing 35.7 percent strongly agree, 32 respondents representing 32.7 percent agree that the nutritional concerns of a household as a factor that affects foodways in Nigerian food marketing. 8 respondents representing 8.2 percent were neutral, 6 respondents representing 6.1 percent disagreed and 17 respondents representing 17.3 percent strongly disagree.

Table 3 Response on the household disposable income as a factor that affects Foodways in Nigerian food marketing.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	34	34.7	34.7	34.7
	Agree	30	30.6	30.6	65.3
	Neutral	11	11.2	11.2	76.5
	Disagree	9	9.2	9.2	85.7
	strongly disagree	14	14.3	14.3	100.0
Total		98	100.0	100.0	

From Table 3 indicated that 34 respondents out of 98 representing 34.7 percent strongly agree, 30 respondents representing 30.6 percent agree that the household disposable income is a factor that affects foodways in Nigerian food marketing. 11 respondents representing 11.2 percent were neutral, 9 respondents representing 9.2 percent disagreed and 14 respondents representing 14 percent strongly disagree.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

Nutritional concerns of a household have no significant effect on foodways in Nigerian Food Marketing

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.999 ^a	.998	.998	.06221

a. Predictors: (Constant), TIV,GSF,TIQ,DSO

Table 5: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	192.294	4	48.073	12421.457	.000 ^b
	Residual	.360	94	.004		
	Total	192.654	98			

a. Dependent Variable: TNOA
b. Predictors: (Constant), TIV,GSF,TIQ,DSO

Table 6: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.051	.018		2.872	.005
	TIV	.172	.027	.178	6.334	.000
	GSF	.304	.021	.305	14.245	.000
	TIQ ₁	.362	.028	.374	13.139	.000
	DSO	.149	.024	.152	6.232	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TNOA.

Where:

- TNOA = The nutritional concerns of a household as a factor that affects foodways in Nigeria food marketing
- TIV = There is variety of agricultural products that takes care of household in your area
- GSF = Good storage facilities are available for household products
- TIQ = There is quality equipment for harvesting of crops in your locality.
- DSO = Delivery services of harvest to consumers is safe

Statistical criteria {first order test}

Coefficient of multiple determinants {r²}

The R² {R-Squared} which measures the overall goodness of fit of the entire regression, shows the value as .998 and adjusted to .998. This means that R² accounts for 99.8 percent approximately 100 percent. This indicates that the independent variables accounts for about 100 percent of the variation in the dependent variable. Which shows goodness of fit?

The student's t-test:

The test is carried out, to check for the individual significance of the variables. Statistically, the t-statistics of the variables under consideration is interpreted based on the following statement of hypothesis.

H₀: The individual parameters are not significant.

H₁: The individual parameters are significant.

Decision Rule:

If t-calculated > t-tabulated, we reject the null hypothesis {H₀} and accept the alternative hypothesis {H₁}, and if otherwise, we select the null hypothesis {H₀} and reject the alternative hypothesis {H₁}.

Level of significance = α at 5percent = $\frac{0.05}{2} = 0.025$

Degree of freedom: n-k

Where n: sample size.

K: Number of parameter.

98-4 = 94 = 2.326

The calculated value for t-test:

Table 7: The t-test is summarized in the table below:

Variables	t-cal	t-tab	Remark
(Constant)	2.872	± 2.326	Significant
TIV	6.334	± 2.326	Significant
GSF	14.245	± 2.326	Significant
TIQ,	13.139	± 2.326	Significant
DSO	6.232	± 2.326	Significant

The t-statistics is used to test for individual significance of the estimated parameters. From the table above, we can infer that the following parameters were statistically significant, we now agree that there is variety of agricultural products that takes care of household in your area; Good storage facilities are available for household products; there is quality equipment for harvesting of crops in your locality and delivery services of harvest to consumers is safe.

F-statistics (ANOVA)

The F-statistics is used to test for simultaneous significance of all the estimated parameters.

The hypothesis is stated:

$$H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4$$

$$H_1: \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4$$

Level of significance: α at 5 percent

$$\text{Degree of freedom: } \frac{k-1}{N-K} = \frac{4-1}{98-4} = (94, 3) = 2.7858$$

Decision Rule:

If the f-calculated is greater than the f-tabulated {f-cal > f-tab} reject the null hypothesis {H0} that the overall estimate is not significant and if otherwise conclude that the overall estimate is statistically significant.

Decision

From the result, f-calculated {12421.457} is greater that the f-tabulated {2.7858}, that is, f-cal > f-tab. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis {H0} and accept alternate hypothesis which means that the overall estimate has a good fit which also implies that our independent variables are simultaneously significant. We now conclude from the analysis that Nutritional concerns of a household have significant effect foodways in Nigerian food marketing.

Hypothesis Two 2. Multicultural society has no significant effect on foodways in Nigerian food marketing

Table 8: Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.999 ^a	.997	.997	.06791
a. Predictors: (Constant),VTH, CAN, TIT, BAO				

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	168.321	4	42.080	9125.514	.000 ^b
	Residual	.429	93	.005		
	Total	168.750	97			
a. Dependent Variable: MSAA						
b. Predictors: (Constant), VTH,CAN,TIT,BAO						

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.083	.023		-3.570	.001
	VTH	.166	.035	.173	4.798	.000
	CAN	.330	.024	.315	13.937	.000
	TIT	.297	.026	.288	11.603	.000
	BAO	.227	.029	.236	7.747	.000
a. Dependent Variable: MSAA						

Where

MSAA = Multicultural society as a factor that affects foodways in Nigeria food marketing

VTH = Various tribes have their own cultural foods and norms

CAN = Consumption and nutrition are shared by all members of a particular society

TIT = The inability to speak the local language makes the distribution of food produce in some areas

BAO = Buying agents of agricultural produce in various society remains a bottleneck to foodways

Statistical criteria {first order test}

Coefficient of multiple determinants {r²}

The R² {R-Squared} which measures the overall goodness of fit of the entire regression, shows the value as .997 and adjusted to .997. This means that R² accounts for 99.7 percent approximately 98 percent. This indicates that the independent variables accounts for about 100 percent of the variation in the dependent variable. Which shows goodness of fit?

The student's t-test:

The test is carried out, to check for the individual significance of the variables. Statistically, the t-statistics of the variables under consideration is interpreted based on the following statement of hypothesis.

H₀: The individual parameters are not significant.

H₁: The individual parameters are significant.

Decision Rule:

If t-calculated > t-tabulated, we reject the null hypothesis {H₀} and accept the alternative hypothesis {H₁}, and if otherwise, we select the null hypothesis {H₀} and reject the alternative hypothesis {H₁}.

Level of significance = α at 5percent = $\frac{0.05}{2} = 0.025$

Degree of freedom: n-k

Where n: sample size.

K: Number of parameter.

$98-4 = 94 = 2.326$

The calculated value for t-test:

Table 11: The t-test is summarized in the table below:

Variables	t-cal	t-tab	Remark
(Constant)	-3.570	± 2.326	Significant
VTH	4.798	± 2.326	Significant
CAN	13.937	± 2.326	Significant
TIT	11.603	± 2.326	Significant
BAO	7.747	± 2.326	Significant

The t-statistics is used to test for individual significance of the estimated parameters. From the table above, we can infer that the following parameters were statistically significant, we now agree that Various tribes have their own cultural foods and norms; Consumption and nutrition are shared by all members of a particular society; The inability to speak the local language makes the distribution of food produce in some areas and Buying agents of agricultural produce in various society remains a bottled neck to foodways

F-statistics (ANOVA)

The F-statistics is used to test for simultaneous significance of all the estimated parameters.

The hypothesis is stated;

$H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4$

$H_1: \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4$

Level of significance: α at 5 percent

Degree of freedom: $\frac{k-1}{N-K} = \frac{4-1}{98-4} = (94, 3) = 2.7858$

Decision Rule:

If the f-calculated is greater than the f-tabulated {f-cal > f-tab} reject the null hypothesis {H0} that the overall estimate is not significant and if otherwise conclude that the overall estimate is statistically significant.

Decision

From the result, f-calculated {9125.514} is greater that the f-tabulated {2.7858}, that is, f-cal > f-tab. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis {H₀} and accept alternate hypothesis which means that the overall estimate has a good fit which also implies that our independent variables are simultaneously significant. We now conclude from the analysis that Multicultural society has significant effect on foodways in Nigerian food marketing.

Hypothesis 3: Household disposable income has no significant effect on foodways in Nigerian food marketing

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.999 ^a	.997	.997	.07270

a. Predictors: (Constant), YAA, TII,TIO,TIP

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	168.631	4	42.158	7975.741	.000 ^b
	Residual	.492	93	.005		
	Total	169.122	97			

a. Dependent Variable: THDI
b. Predictors: (Constant), YAA, TII,TIO,TIP

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.008	.027		.300	.765
	YAA	.377	.037	.415	10.273	.000
	TII	.342	.024	.339	14.515	.000
	TIO	.316	.025	.299	12.476	.000
	ITF	-.037	.035	-.041	-1.060	.292

a. Dependent Variable: THDI

Where

THDI = The household disposable income as a factor that affects foodways in Nigeria

YAA = You are affected by unemployment in your household

TII = There is irregular payment of salaries or inflow of income that sustains the household for your food purchasing.

TIO = There is practice of household subsistence farming

ITF = Inadequate transportation facilities increases the cost of food purchasing.

Statistical criteria {first order test}

Coefficient of multiple determinants {r²}

The R² {R-Squared} which measures the overall goodness of fit of the entire regression, shows the value as .997 and adjusted to .997 This means that R² accounts for 99.7 percent approximately 100 percent. This indicates that the independent variables accounts for about 100 percent of the variation in the dependent variable. Which shows goodness of fit?

The student's t-test:

The test is carried out, to check for the individual significance of the variables. Statistically, the t-statistics of the variables under consideration is interpreted based on the following statement of hypothesis.

H₀: The individual parameters are not significant.

H₁: The individual parameters are significant.

Decision Rule:

If t-calculated > t-tabulated, we reject the null hypothesis {H₀} and accept the alternative hypothesis {H₁}, and if otherwise, we select the null hypothesis {H₀} and reject the alternative hypothesis {H₁}.

Level of significance = α at 5percent = $\frac{0.05}{2} = 0.025$

Degree of freedom: n-k

Where n: sample size.

K: Number of parameter.

98-4 = 94 = 2.326

The calculated value for t-test:

Table 3. The t-test is summarized in the table below:

Variables	t-cal	t-tab	Remark
(Constant)	.300	± 2.326	Significant
YAA	10.273	± 2.326	Significant
TII	14.515	± 2.326	Significant
TIO	12.476	± 2.326	Significant
ITF	-1.060	± 2.326	Significant

The t-statistics is used to test for individual significance of the estimated parameters. From the table above, we can infer that the following parameters were statistically significant, we now agree that the household disposable income as a factor that affects foodways in Nigeria; You are affected by unemployment in your household; there is irregular payment of salaries or inflow of income that sustains the household for your food purchasing; there is practice of household subsistence farming and Inadequate transportation facilities increases the cost of food purchasing.

F-statistics (ANOVA)

The F-statistics is used to test for simultaneous significance of all the estimated parameters.

The hypothesis is stated;

H₀: $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4$

H₁: $\beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4$

Level of significance: α at 5 percent

Degree of freedom: $\frac{k-1}{N-K} = \frac{4-1}{98-4} = (94, 3) = 2.7858$

Decision Rule:

If the f-calculated is greater than the f-tabulated {f-cal > f-tab} reject the null hypothesis {H₀} that the overall estimate is not significant and if otherwise conclude that the overall estimate is statistically significant.

Decision

From the result, f-calculated {7975.741} is greater than the f-tabulated {2.7858}, that is, $f_{cal} > f_{tab}$. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis $\{H_0\}$ and accept alternate hypothesis which means that the overall estimate has a good fit which also implies that our independent variables are simultaneously significant. We now conclude from the analysis that Household disposable income has significant effect on foodways in Nigerian food marketing.

Discussion of Findings

From the result of hypothesis one, f-calculated {12421.457} is greater than the f-tabulated {2.7858}, that is, $f_{cal} > f_{tab}$. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis $\{H_0\}$ and accept alternate hypothesis which means that the overall estimate has a good fit which also implies that our independent variables are simultaneously significant. We now conclude from the analysis that nutritional concerns of a household have significant effect on foodways in Nigerian food marketing. The result was supported in the literature by Weaver (2012), Food is the fuel for our bodies. When we live, we burn calories and they must be replaced. No fuel, no run. No food, no live. It is important to have a balanced diet because if you get to overweight you could get obese. Restricted diets can cause allergies...when improving your diet, instead of thinking of "restricting" your diet, "expand" your diet.

From the result of hypothesis two, f-calculated {9125.514} is greater than the f-tabulated {2.7858}, that is, $f_{cal} > f_{tab}$. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis $\{H_0\}$ and accept alternate hypothesis which means that the overall estimate has a good fit which also implies that our independent variables are simultaneously significant. We now conclude from the analysis that Multicultural society has significant effect on foodways in Nigerian food marketing. Akinnusi, Olubukunola and Adebukola (2017) opine that in the government sector, the management of multicultural society has been an integral part of the historical development of Nigeria as a nation, even in colonial times, when the colonialists considered it prudent to use indirect rule to manage the discrete entities joined together as Nigeria. After independence, the government agonized over the choice of the best form of government appropriate for the hugely multicultural country, also diverse in flora and fauna. It wanted to ensure that the nation's multicultural society does not constitute a cog in the wheel of national progress.

In economics, disposable income refers to household income after deducting mandatory taxes, such as state and federal income tax, Social Security and Medicare. Another term that you might often see is "discretionary income," which refers to household income after paying for necessities, such as food, housing costs, insurance and utilities. It's important to note that the boundary between mandatory and voluntary deductions is quite strict: Even though you may consider deductions made for health insurance and your 401k to be essential, they are still considered as optional expenses because you choose to have insurance coverage and a retirement plan. Lainie, (2018). This assertion was supported by the result, f-calculated {7975.741} is greater than the f-tabulated {2.7858}, that is, $f_{cal} > f_{tab}$. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis $\{H_0\}$ and accept alternate hypothesis which means that the overall estimate has a good fit which also implies that our independent variables are simultaneously significant. We now conclude from the analysis that Household disposable income has significant effect on foodways in Nigerian food marketing. Furthermore, in the literature, review, Agbogo, Udouso, and Tiku (2013) indicates that price naturally has an inverse relationship with consumption expenditure, where an increase in income results in less of the commodity consumed.

Conclusion

The study concluded that the nutritional concerns, multicultural society and the household disposable income are factors that affect food ways in Nigerian food marketing. Food availability for households in urban and rural areas means assurance that they can access sufficient food through their own production or through purchase from markets, given sufficient purchasing power. Food access is ensured when households, and all individuals within them, have adequate resources to obtain appropriate foods for a nutritious diet.

Recommendation

1. The nutritional concerns should be a target of any household because it is important to have a balanced diet and equally expand your diet.
2. Multicultural society should be encouraged because many advantages lie in diversity as many individuals from a different angle of the country possess different skills which can be maximized by these institutions.
3. Government should create room for self-reliance by increasing vocational skills training to enhance household income levels to meet up with their needs.

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